

Recent studies on *Pelargonium graveolens* L'Hér.: a review on chemical composition and biological activity

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Abstract

Pelargonium graveolens L'Hér. (rose geranium) is an aromatic plant widely used in traditional medicine and essential oil production. This review highlights its phytochemical diversity and pharmacological potential based on recent studies (2020–2025). The database search was conducted using PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus. The survey revealed that essential oils are dominated by citronellol, geraniol, linalool, and isomenthone, while non-volatile compounds include flavonoids, phenolic, acyltartaric and acylcitric acids, and tannins. The plant's extracts and oils demonstrate a wide range of biological activities—antioxidant and anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticancer, and neuroprotective potential as well as antidiabetic and insecticidal properties. These effects are connected to its rich secondary metabolite profile, notably flavonol glycosides, hydroxycinnamic derivatives, and terpenoids. Given its complex phytochemical profile and extensive pharmacological properties, *P. graveolens* shows significant promise as a source of bioactive agents for the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries.

Keywords

Pelargonium graveolens, rose geranium, phytochemistry, biological activity

Introduction

Medicinal plants are natural sources of chemical compounds responsible for a wide range of biological activities. The historical and contemporary significance of plant-derived compounds in treating diseases, including cancer and viral infections, underscores their growing role in modern herbal drug development due to their efficacy and lower side-effect profiles compared to synthetic drugs (Dar et al. 2017).

Pelargonium graveolens L'Hér. (rose geranium) is an aromatic plant extensively cultivated for its essential oil, valued in the cosmetic, food, and pharmaceutical industries (DAFF 2012; Sandasi et al. 2023). Native to Southern

Africa, the species has long held a place in traditional medicine for its diverse therapeutic properties, based on specific chemical compounds (Amel et al. 2022; Sandasi et al. 2023).

Most phytochemical investigations have emphasized that the essential oil composition is dominated by citronellol, geraniol, linalool, and isomenthone (Amel et al. 2022; Sandasi et al. 2023). There is notable variation in their content across geographical locations, cultivars, and phenological stages (Al-Mijalli et al. 2022; Fayoumi et al. 2022; Lothe and Verma 2023). Beyond volatiles, the species contains flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, and other secondary metabolites that contribute to its therapeutic potential (Gevrenova et al. 2024; M'hamdi et al. 2024; Draiaia et al. 2025).

Recent reviews on the traditional usage, phytochemical profile, and pharmacology of *P. graveolens* have highlighted its anticancer, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory effects, along with antimicrobial and neuroprotective properties supported by in vitro and in vivo studies (M'hammed Amine et al. 2020; Amel et al. 2022; Roman et al. 2023; Sandasi et al. 2023). The antioxidant effects have been confirmed through radical scavenging activity, reducing power, and metal-chelating capacity (Checkouri et al. 2020; Gevrenova et al. 2024). Enzyme-inhibitory activities are relevant to metabolic and neurodegenerative disorders (Ferreira et al. 2021; Karadağ et al. 2023; Gevrenova et al. 2024). Moreover, other studies have demonstrated insecticidal and cosmetic properties of rose geranium, expanding its applications (Bošković et al. 2023; Sandasi et al. 2023; M'hamdi et al. 2024). Thus, given its rich ethnobotanical background, specific chemical composition, and scientifically validated pharmacological attributes, *P. graveolens* remains a subject of growing interest in natural product research.

This review provides an integrated overview of *Pelargonium graveolens* phytochemistry and pharmacological value, drawing from present-day literature to highlight its therapeutic potential and perspectives for future investigations.

The database search was conducted for the period 2020–2025 (up to July 2025) using PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus. The search terms included all combinations of the following keywords: *Pelargonium graveolens*, rose geranium, phytochemistry, phytochemicals, pharmacology, and biological activity.

All titles with abstracts were imported into the citation manager program Mendeley (Elsevier-Mendeley Ltd., London, UK), and all duplicates were removed. The bibliographies of imported articles were also screened for other relevant studies. All articles were critically read and analyzed. There were inclusion and exclusion criteria for selection of the important relevant references. Inclusion criteria were all relevant studies reporting the biological activity of an extract, fraction, or composition of compounds, as well as single compounds from *P. graveolens*; only studies published in English were taken into consideration.

Exclusion criteria were the following types of experimental papers: research related to *P. graveolens* as an ornamental plant or on chemicals influencing plant growth, cultivation papers, and articles about the biosynthesis of *P. graveolens*.

The studies were divided into two main parts: phytochemistry and biological activity.

Results and discussion

After duplicate removal, 58 articles were further screened by title and abstract. Finally, 29 studies met the inclusion criteria.

Taxonomy, botanical profile, and distribution

Pelargonium graveolens L'Hér. is known as “rose geranium,” “rose-scented pelargonium,” and “sweet-scented geranium” (English) and belongs to the Geraniaceae family (Sandasi et al. 2023). The genus *Pelargonium* L'Hér. ex Aiton, comprising more than 290 species, is one of the seven genera belonging to the family. The first published data for the genus and species appear in *Hortus Kewensis* in 1789 (www.powo.science.kew.org).

Pelargonium graveolens L'Hér. is also known by the following synonyms: *Geranospermum terebintaceum* Kuntze, *Geranium asperum* Poir., *Geranium graveolens* (L'Hér.) Thunb., *Geranium radula* Roth, *Geranium terebinthinaceum* Cav., *Hoarea intermixta* Sweet, *Pelargonium asperum* Ehrh. ex Spreng., *Pelargonium intermedium* R.Knuth, *Pelargonium terebinthinaceum* Small (www.worldfloraonline.org).

The plant is described as an erect, much-branched, strongly rose-scented shrub, 0.6–1.3 m high. Stems are herbaceous, becoming woody, densely villous, and interspersed with glandular hairs. Leaves are simple; the lamina is cordiform, up to 55 × 100 mm, palmatipartite to pinnatisect, with segments at least 3 mm wide, with obtuse or acute apex and irregularly serrated margins; adaxially sparsely villous, green; abaxially almost lanate, grayish green; petioles up to 80 mm long. Inflorescences are 3–7-flowered pseudo-umbels; peduncles up to 40 mm long. Petals are 5, white to pinkish; the posterior 2 are spatulate, up to 30 × 8 mm with obtuse to emarginate apex, marked red; the anterior 3 are spatulate, up to 22 × 5 mm. Flowering period is August–January (www.worldfloraonline.org).

The native distribution area of rose geranium is from East Zimbabwe to the Eastern Cape Province. It is a subshrub or shrub and grows primarily in the subtropical biome. The plant inhabits relatively moist habitats in shaded or semi-shaded areas. The species has been introduced into the Canary Islands, Corsica, Costa Rica, Cuba, the Dominican Republic, Haiti, Southwestern Mexico, Puerto Rico, and Sicily (Sandasi et al. 2023; www.powo.science.kew.org; www.worldfloraonline.org).

Historical aspects of commercial use

Initially, rose geranium was commercialized in France, where the first distillation trials were conducted in Lyon (1819), and the first plantation was established in Grasse (1844) (Gildemeister and Hoffmann 1900). Subsequently, manufacturing moved to Algeria and Réunion Island, which were considered the largest producers, favoring the Bourbon-type variety (citronellol:geraniol ratio ≈ 1:1). Later, other countries, including Kenya, Spain, Egypt, Morocco, Belgium, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Russia, began commercial production of geranium oil. In the last decade, the major international producers of rose geranium oil have been South Africa, India, China, and Egypt (DAFF 2012). Rose-scented geranium essential oil is globally in high demand as a substitute for the luxurious

rose oil in the perfume trade, as well as for therapeutic applications (Sandasi et al. 2023). Thus, the geranium oil market is expected to grow by more than 8% over the next 5 years, according to the Global Industry Analysis and Forecast (2024–2030) (www.maximizemarketresearch.com).

A summary of scientific conclusions was made by the Committee on Herbal Medicinal Products (HMPC) on the medicinal application of pelargonium root. “Pelargonium root” is the common name for the root of *Pelargonium sidoides* DC and *Pelargonium reniforme* Curt. Its therapeutic activity is for coughs and colds (www.ema.europa.eu).

Phytochemistry of *Pelargonium graveolens*

The main groups of secondary metabolites of rose geranium—terpenoids, phenolic acids, quinic and citric acid conjugates, flavonoids, and tannins—are presented in Table 1 based on the reviewed studies. Special focus was given to phenolic compounds, important but often underestimated phytochemicals in the plant.

Mono- and sesquiterpenes

The essential oil of *P. graveolens* is secreted in the glandular trichomes (Amel et al. 2022). Its yield in the leaves reached up to 1.01% (Jaradat et al. 2022). The chemical profile of rose geranium essential oil has been broadly studied due to commercialization and the necessity of establishing quality standards. Mainly, monoterpenes, alcohols, and esters have been identified in the essential oil composition (Al-Mijalli

et al. 2022; Amel et al. 2022; Fayoumi et al. 2022; Jaradat et al. 2022) (Table 1). A study reported up to 41.31% oxygenated monoterpenes and 20.84% monoterpene hydrocarbons in the full flowering and vegetative stages, respectively (Al-Mijalli et al. 2022). Nevertheless, a recent investigation described higher values of oxygenated monoterpenes (52.54%) and lower values of monoterpene hydrocarbons (10.17%) (Draiaia et al. 2025).

Predominantly, the monoterpenes are represented by citronellol (1), geraniol (2), isomenthone (4), linalool (9), and borneol (10) (Fig. 1, Table 1). Various oxygenated and non-oxygenated sesquiterpenes are also present in rose geranium oil (Fig. 1, Table 1). Among the oxygenated sesquiterpenes, agarospirol (71), α -cadinol (72), epi- α -cadinol (73), 10-epi- γ -eudesmol (83), heptaminol (87), caryophyllene epoxide (101), and nerolidyl acetate (103) have been found as dominant constituents. Their quantities varied from 0.3 to 8.27% (Amel et al. 2022). Regarding non-oxygenated sesquiterpenes, the following compounds have been detected: δ -selinene (105), aromadendrene (110), β -caryophyllene (124), and ledene (157), with amounts up to 7.2% (Amel et al. 2022).

In a chemotaxonomy study involving 70 geranium oils from various cultivation sites in South Africa, Egypt, India, Réunion Island, China, and Madagascar, GC-MS and vibrational spectroscopy were used to determine oil compositions (Sandasi et al. 2011). Even though the content varied quantitatively between samples, seven major compounds were identified: citronellol (19.5%–51.3%), geraniol (5.9%–32.1%), linalool (0.8%–10.3%), isomenthone (0.6%–8.0%), citronellyl

Figure 1. Mono- and sesquiterpenes in *P. graveolens*.

Table 1. Secondary metabolites in *Pelargonium graveolens*.

Group of compounds/compound	Plant part/ identification method	Reference
Monoterpenes		
Alcohols		
citronellol (1), geraniol (2), citronellyl formate (3), iso-menthone (4), menthol (5), menthone (6), isoborneol (7), isogeraniol (8), linalool (9), borneol (10), elemol (11), eugenol (12), lavandulol (13), epoxylinoolol (14), 3- <i>p</i> -menthanol (15), isomenthol (16), neomenthol (17), neo-isomenthol (18), menthomenthol (19), 8-hydroxy-neomenthol (20), <i>p</i> -menth-1-ene-8-ol (21), myrtenol (22), nerolidol (23), nerol (24), neo-isopulegol (25), α -terpineol (26), terpinen-4-ol (27), thymol (28), carvacrol (29);	Leaves, aerial parts/GC/MS, HPTLC	Amel et al. 2022; Al-Mijalli et al. 2022; Fayoumi et al. 2022; Jaradat et al. 2022; Karadağ et al. 2023; Sandasia et al. 2023; Draiaia et al. 2025
Oxides		
geranic oxide limetol (30), <i>cis</i> -linalool oxide (31), <i>trans</i> -linalool oxide (32), nerol oxide (33), <i>trans</i> -rose oxide (34);	Leaves, aerial parts/GC/MS	Amel et al. 2022; Draiaia et al. 2025
Carboxylic acids and esters		
bornyl acetate (35), citronellyl acetate (36), citronellyl butanoate (37), citronellyl butyrate (38), citronellyl cinnamate (39), citronellyl ester (40), citronellyl formate (41), citronellyl heptanoate (42), citronellyl hexanoate (43), citronellyl isobutyrate (44), citronellyl isoheptanoate (45), citronellyl isohexanoate (46), citronellyl isovalerate (47), citronellyl octanoate (48), citronellyl pentanoate (49), citronellyl propanoate (50), citronellyl propionate (51), citronellyl tiglate (52), citronellyl valerate (53), ethyl geranate (54), geranyl acetate (55), geranyl butanoate (56), geranyl butyrate (57), geranyl ester (58), geranyl formate (59), geranyl heptanoate (60), geranyl hexanoate (61), geranyl isobutanoate (62), geranyl isobutyrate (63), geranyl isoheptanoate (64);	Leaves, aerial parts/GC/MS	Amel et al. 2022
Aldehydes and ketones		
1,8-cineol (65), citral (66), citronellal (67), geranial (68), neral (69), pulegone (70);	Leaves, aerial parts/GC/MS	Amel et al. 2022; Draiaia et al. 2025;
Sesquiterpenes		
Oxygenated sesquiterpenes		
agarospirol (71), α -cadinol (72), <i>epi</i> - α -cadinol (73), τ -cadinol (74), caryophylla-4(12),8(13)-dien-5-ol (75), cubenol (76), 1- <i>epi</i> -cubenol (77), 1,10-di- <i>epi</i> -cubenol (78), cubedol (79), α -eudesmol (80), β -eudesmol (81), γ -eudesmol (82), 10- <i>epi</i> - γ -eudesmol (83), 2Z, 6E-farnesol (84), globulol (85), guaial (86), heptaminol (87), hinesol (88), <i>neo</i> -isopulegol (89), junenol (90), ledol (91), maaliol (92), α -muurolol (93), τ -muurolol (94), (e)-nerolidol (95), spathulenol (96), valerianol (97), viridiflorol (98), alloaromadendrene oxide (99), caryophyllene oxide (100), caryophyllene epoxide (101), humulene epoxide (102), nerolidyl acetate (103);	Leaves/GC/MS	Amel et al. 2022; Jaradat et al. 2022; Karadağ et al. 2023;
Non-oxygenated sesquiterpenes		
eremophilene (104), δ -selinene (105), α -agarofuran (106), α -amorphone (107), δ -amorphone (108), aristolene (109), aromadendrene (110), <i>allo</i> -aromadendrene (111), <i>trans</i> - α -bergamotene (112), bicyclogermacrene (113), β -bourbonene (114), cadalene (115), cadina-1,4-diene (116), α -cadinene (117), β -cadinene (118), γ -cadinene (119), δ -cadinene (120), α -calacorene (121), calamenene (122), α -caryophyllene (123), β -caryophyllene (124), γ -caryophyllene (125), (E)-caryophyllene (126), (Z)-caryophyllene (127), α -cofaene (128), α -copaene (129), β -copaene (130), α -cubebene (131), β -cubebene (132), β -cubebene (133), β -elemene (134), γ -elemene (135), <i>trans</i> - β -elemenone (136), epizonaren (137), (e)- β -farnesene (138), 2- <i>epi</i> - β -funebrene (139), furopelargone A (140), furopelargone B (141), germacrene A (142), germacrene B (143), germacrene D (144), germacrene (145), guaia-6,9-diene (146), α -guaiene (147), <i>cis</i> - β -guaiene (148), α -gurjunene (149), γ -gurjunene (150), α -himachalene (151), α -humulene (152), 14-hydroxy-9- <i>epi</i> -(e)-caryophyllene (153), isocaryophyllene (154), isodene (155), isolongifolene (156), ledene (157), <i>cis</i> -muurola-3,5-diene (158), <i>cis</i> -muurola-4(14),5-diene (159), α -muurolene (160), γ -muurolene (161), selina-3,7(11)-diene (162), α -selinene (163), β -selinene (164), δ -selinene (165), valencene (166), viridiflorol (167), α -ylangene (168);	Aerial parts/GC/MS	Al-Mijalli et al. 2022; Amel et al. 2022; Draiaia et al. 2025
Hydroxybenzoic acids and their glycosides, sugar esters, phenolic aldehydes and alcohols		
gallic acid (169), protocatechuic acid (170), gentisic acid (171), vanillic acid (172), 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (173), 3-hydroxybenzoic acid (174), salicylic acid (175), protocatechuic acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (176), protocatechuic acid- <i>O</i> -dihexoside (177), vanillic acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (178), hydroxybenzoic acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (179), syringic acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside (180), vanilloyl- <i>O</i> -hexose (181), syringyl- <i>O</i> -hexose (182), vanillin (183), vanillyl alcohol-(acetyl)-hexoside (184), phenylethyl- <i>O</i> -pentosyl-hexoside (185), <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenylacetic acid <i>O</i> -hexoside (186);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Hydroxycinnamic acids and their glycosides		
<i>p</i> -coumaric acid (187), <i>m</i> -coumaric acid (188), <i>o</i> -coumaric acid (189), ferulic acid (190), caffeic acid (191), caffeoylglucaric acid (192), dihydrocaffeic acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (193), coumaric acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (194), caffeic acid- <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (195), rosmarinic acid (196), caffeoylquinic acid (197), sinapoyl glucose (198), caffeoyl glucose (199), caffeoylhydroxycitric acid (200), feruloylglucaric acid (201), ferulic acid-(vanillyl)-hexoside (202), gentisic acid-(feruloyl)-hexoside (203);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024; M'hamdi et al. 2024
Aliphatic acids		
tartaric acid (204), malic acid (205), citric/isocitric acid (206);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Gevrenova et al. 2024
Acyltartaric acids		
caftaric acid (207), caffeoyltartaric acid-hexoside (208), dicaffeoyltartaric acid isomers (209), feruloyltartaric acid (210);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Gevrenova et al. 2024; M'hamdi et al. 2024
Acylcitric acids (citric/isocitric acid esters)		
caffeoylcitric/isocitric acid (211), coumaroylcitric/isocitric acid (212), feruloylcitric/isocitric acid (213);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Gevrenova et al. 2024

Group of compounds/compound	Plant part/ identification method	Reference
Flavonoids		
Flavonols		
isoquercitrin (214), hyperoside (215), rutin (216), quercetin-3- <i>O</i> -arabinoside (217), quercetin 3- <i>O</i> -pentosyl (1 → 2) hexoside (218), quercetin <i>O</i> -hexuronide (219), ayanin (220), quercetin dimethyl ether (221), quercetin (222), astragalol (223), kaempferol 3- <i>O</i> -rutinoside (224), kaempferol 3,7-di- <i>O</i> -glucoside (225), kaempferol 3- <i>O</i> -pentoside (226), trifolin (227), kaempferol <i>O</i> -pentosyl hexoside (228), kaempferol dimethyl ether <i>O</i> -hexoside (229), kaempferide (230), kaempferol-3-methyl ether (231), kaempferol-3,4'-dimethyl ether (232), kaempferol-3,7-dimethyl ether (233), kaempferol (234), kaempferol hexuronide (235), myricitrin (236), myricetin 3- <i>O</i> -galactoside (237), myricetin 3- <i>O</i> -glucoside (238), myricetin 3- <i>O</i> -rutinoside (239), myricetin 3- <i>O</i> -pentosyl hexoside (240), myricetin <i>O</i> -pentoside (241), myricetin methylether <i>O</i> -hexoside (242), myricetin dimethyl ether (243), myricetin trimethyl ether (244), myricetin (245), isorhamnetin 3- <i>O</i> -rutinoside (246), isorhamnetin 3- <i>O</i> -glucoside (247), isorhamnetin (248), retusin (249);	Leaves, aerial parts/ UHPLC-HRMS, HPLC- MS	Checkouri et al. 2020; Amel et al. 2022; Sandasi et al. 2023; Gevrenova et al. 2024; M'hamdi et al. 2024
Flavones		
cirsimaritin (250), luteolin 7- <i>O</i> -caffeoylhexoside (251), luteolin (252), diosmetin (253);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Flavanones		
eriodictyol <i>O</i> -hexoside (254), eriodictyol (255), naringenin 7- <i>O</i> -hexoside (256), naringenin (257), hesperidin (258);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Flavan-3-ols		
catechin (259), epigallocatechin (260), galocatechin (261);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Chalcones		
phloretin <i>C</i> -hexoside (262), phloretin 3',5-di- <i>C</i> -hexoside (263);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Coumarins		
scopoletin-(caffeoyl)-hexoside (264), scopoletin <i>O</i> -hexoside isomers (265), aesculetin (268), aesculetin- <i>O</i> -hexoside (269);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Gallotannins		
ellagic acid (270), glucogallin (271), prodelphinidin (272), galloyl- <i>O</i> -hexose (273), digalloyl- <i>O</i> -hexose (274), tetragalloyl-hexose (275), digallic acid (276), methylgallate (277), epigallocatechin dimer (278), epigallocatechin trimer (279);	Leaves/UHPLC-HRMS	Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024
Lactones		
carnosol (280), epirosmanol (281), 6,7-dimethoxy-7-epi-rosmanol (282), 11,12-dimethyl rosmanol (283), 7-methyl-rosmanol (284), rosmadial (285), rosmanol (286);	Leaves, aerial parts/ UPLC/MS	Amel et al. 2022

formate (3.5%–19.9%), geranyl formate (0.10%–8.99%), and guaia-6,9-diene (0.2%–9.6%) (Sandasi et al. 2011). Likewise, Boukhris et al. (2013) described β -citronellol (21.9%), citronellyl formate (13.2%), geraniol (11.1%), 10-epi- γ -eudesmol (7.9%), geranyl formate (6.2%), and linalool (5.6%) as main constituents of geranium oil.

Regardless of geographic origin, Al-Mijalli et al. (2022) and Fayoumi et al. (2022) examined the chemical composition of *P. graveolens* essential oil during different phenological stages and reported variability between the vegetative and full flowering stages. The quantity of oxygenated monoterpenes reached up to 41.31% in the full flowering stage, while non-oxygenated sesquiterpenes (30.19%) were highest at the beginning of the flowering stage (Al-Mijalli et al. 2022). Changes in the citronellol-to-geraniol ratio were also monitored at different stages of leaf development (Fekri et al. 2019). The results indicated that geraniol content was highest in young leaves, whereas citronellol concentrations increased with leaf age.

Lately, Roman et al. (2023) categorized geranium essential oil into three main types based on geographic origin and chemical profile: (1) the Chinese type, characterized by high citronellol content (30–40%); (2) the African type, found in Algeria, Morocco, and Egypt, distinguished by the presence of 10-epi- γ -eudesmol (4–5%); and (3) the Bourbon type, produced

in Réunion Island or Madagascar, notable for higher concentrations of guaia-6,9-diene (5–7%), geraniol (15–18%), and linalool (0.5–8%). Plants cultivated in Lebanon were characterized by citronellol (30.5%), citronellyl formate (15.9%), *trans*-geraniol (12.8%), linalool (8.6%), and isomenthone (8.0%) (Fayoumi et al. 2022). Oils of Palestinian origin contained 35.4% citronellol and 20.2% geraniol (Jaradat et al. 2022). The chemical composition of the essential oil obtained from the aerial parts of rose geranium grown in Morocco had the following major compounds: epi- γ -eudesmol (16.67%), geraniol (12.54%), β -citronellol (12.34%), citronellyl formate (7.70%), geranyl tiglate (5.21%), and linalool (4.06%) (M'hamdi et al. 2024). Alternatively, 32 compounds constituting 99.23% of rose geranium essential oil from Egypt have been identified. The major constituents were citronellol (29.90%), *trans*-geraniol (18.03%), 10-epi- γ -eudesmol (8.27%), isomenthone (5.44%), and linalool (5.13%), with an oil yield of 0.26% (v/w) (Draiaia et al. 2025).

Phenolic compounds

The presence of phenolic acids and flavonoids beyond volatile oils was summarized by Amel et al. (2022). Recently, the list was fully supplemented by Gevrenova et al. (2024).

Phenolic acids

The most common phenolic acids are derived from benzoic acid or cinnamic acid and are referred to as hydroxybenzoic acids or hydroxycinnamic acids, respectively (Kumar and Goel 2019). *p*-Coumaric acids (187, 188, and 189), ferulic acid (190), caffeic acid (191), and rosmarinic acid (196) are the most common hydroxycinnamic acids in rose geranium (Table 1, Fig. 2). Hydroxybenzoic acids are represented by gentisic acid (171), gallic acid (169), protocatechuic acid (170), and vanillic acid (172), along with their glycosides. Ferulic acid-(vanillyl)-hexoside (202) and gentisic acid-(feruloyl)-hexoside (203) have also been annotated, together with phenylethyl-*O*-pentosylhexoside (185).

It is noteworthy that the aliphatic acids in the leaves were largely represented by tartaric acid (204), malic acid (205), and citric/isocitric acid (206) (Table 1, Fig. 2). Altogether, phenolic and aliphatic acids and their derivatives accounted for 65.55% of the assayed compounds in LC-MS phytochemical profiling (Gevrenova et al. 2024).

Acyltartaric and acylcitric/isocitric acids

Recently, acylcitric/isocitric acids, including the esters of caffeic, coumaric, and ferulic acids, were reported for the first time in *P. graveolens* (Gevrenova et al. 2024). They accounted for 2.30% of the assayed secondary metabolites in leaf profiling. Additionally, dicaffeoyl-, coumaroyl-, and feruloyltartaric acids had not been previously annotated. It is worth noting that acyltartaric acids accounted for up to 18.16% of the compounds in the profile, dominated by caftaric acid (207) and its isomers (12.12%).

Flavonoids

Flavonoids are the most varied and broadly distributed phenolic compounds, playing important roles in many biological processes and in plant responses to environmental factors (Shen et al. 2022). Based on the literature survey, rose geranium contains flavonoids from five different groups: flavanols, flavanones, flavones, flavan-3-ols, and chalcones (Table 1, Fig. 2). These compounds were found in the leaves and aerial parts of the plant, identified by hyphenated techniques (HPLC-PDA-ESI-MS, UH-PLC-HRMS, etc.) (Amel et al. 2022; Sandasi et al. 2023; Gevrenova et al. 2024; M'hamdi et al. 2024).

Flavonols and their glycosides

Aglycones of flavonols presented in rose geranium include quercetin (222), myricetin (245), kaempferol (234), and ayanin (220) (Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024). Furthermore, flavonol glycosides have been revealed as the most abundant group of flavonoids in leaves (Amel et al. 2022). Likewise, they may also be distinguished in rose petals (Androustopoulos et al. 2021). The presence of myricetin dimethyl ether (243) and myricetin trimethyl ether (244) should also be mentioned.

In leaf profiling, kaempferol dimethyl ether (2.61%) and myricetin *O*-rhamnoside (myricitrin) (1.04%) predominated. The relative abundance of flavonoids accounted for 11.92% (Gevrenova et al. 2024).

Flavanones, flavones, and flavan-3-ols

The flavanones are represented by naringenin (257) and eriodictyol (255), their glycosides, and hesperidin (258) (Table 1, Fig. 2). Some minor flavones have also been identified in leaf extracts, including cirsimaritin (250), luteolin 7-*O*-caffeoylhexoside (251), luteolin (252), and diosmetin (253) (Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024).

Flavan-3-ols are represented by catechin (259) in significant quantity (9.80×10^{-3} mg/g), as well as epigallocatechin (260) and gallocatechin (261) (Amel et al. 2022).

Additionally, chalcones are represented by phloretin *C*-hexoside (262) and phloretin 3',5-di-*C*-hexoside (263) (Table 1).

Coumarins

Based on recent studies, coumarins characterized in rose geranium include scopoletin-(caffeoyl)-hexoside (264), scopoletin *O*-hexoside isomers (265), aesculetin (268), and aesculetin-*O*-hexoside (269) (Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024) (Table 1).

Gallotannins

The literature survey on *P. graveolens* revealed proanthocyanidins, or condensed tannins, among which the most common are catechin derivatives, for example, prodelfinidin (272) (Table 1). Moreover, ellagic acid (270), glucogallin (271), galloyl-*O*-hexose (273), digalloyl-*O*-hexose (274), tetragalloyl-hexose (275), and digallic acid (276) have also been identified (Amel et al. 2022; Gevrenova et al. 2024) (Fig. 2).

Gallotannins may reach up to 1.82% of the total established compounds (Gevrenova et al. 2024).

Diterpene lactones

Recently, several diterpene lactones—carnosol (280), epirosmanol (281), rosmadial (285), and rosmanol (286)—have been reported in rose geranium (Amel et al. 2022) (Table 1).

Biological activity of *Pelargonium graveolens*

Based on the literature survey, *P. graveolens* has been studied in a variety of pharmacological areas, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory, anticancer and neuroprotective activity, as well as antidiabetic, antimicrobial, and insecticidal effects (Amel et al. 2022; Karadağ et al. 2023; Sandasi et al. 2023; Gevrenova et al. 2024; Draiaia et al. 2025). The results from the reviewed trials on biological activity are presented in Table 2.

Figure 2. Phenolic compounds in *P. graveolens*.

Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity. Enzyme-inhibitory effects

Rose geranium exhibited radical scavenging activity in vitro DPPH and ABTS assays, reducing power (CUPRAC, FRAP), and metal-chelating capacity. Its antioxidant potential was further confirmed by the phosphomolybdenum test (Sandasi et al. 2023; Gevrenova et al. 2024). Recently, radical inhibition activity of rose geranium leaf essential oil was measured by DPPH and FRAP assays, with results of $22.93 \pm 8.08 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $18.79 \pm 2.89 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively (Draiaia et al. 2025). Alternatively, the antioxidant effect of rose geranium leaf extract was assessed in DPPH ($273.45 \pm 4.31 \text{ mg TE/g}$), ABTS•+ ($531.97 \pm 10.97 \text{ mg TE/g}$), FRAP ($292.21 \pm 4.77 \text{ mg TE/g}$), and CUPRAC ($413.22 \pm 7.22 \text{ mg TE/g}$) (Gevrenova et al. 2024) (Table 2). These effects may be related to the presence of myricetin- and quercetin glycosides, together with gallic, protocatechuic, and caffeic acid derivatives. Indeed, caffeic acid conjugates showed higher antiradical activity against superoxide and hydroxyl radicals than caffeic acid itself (Świdorski et al. 2024).

As antioxidant capacity is usually attributed to phenolic compounds, the total flavonoid and phenolic contents in a methanol–aqueous extract were determined to be 9.49 mg RE/g and 83.86 mg GAE/g extract, respectively (Gevrenova et al. 2024). In comparison, another study reported total phenolic contents of 156.42 mg GAE/g (aqueous extract) and 385.09 mg GAE/g (ethanol extract) (M'hamdi et al. 2024). The total phenolic and flavonoid contents were also reported by El Aanachi et al. (2020) for methanol (36.55 and 381.25 mg GAE/g , respectively) and hexane extracts (18.02 and 330.08 mg QE/g , respectively).

Similarly, El Aanachi et al. (2020) studied the reducing power of different rose geranium extracts in CUPRAC (EC_{50} : $20.29 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and FRAP (EC_{50} : $43.38 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Prominent results were obtained for the methanol extract in both tested methods. Additionally, *P. graveolens* aqueous extracts (decoctions and infusions) were assessed based on their rich polyphenolic content (Checkouri et al. 2020). Antioxidant capacity was determined by different tests, including DPPH and human red blood cell hemolysis. The decoction slightly improved polyphenol yields as well as antioxidant capacity in the DPPH test compared to the infusion extract.

Table 2. Biological activity of *Pelargonium graveolens*.

Compound/Extract	Results	Reference
Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity, Enzyme-inhibitory effect		
aqueous extracts (decoction and infusion)	Antioxidant capacity was assessed by different tests, including DPPH and human red blood cell hemolysis	Checkouri et al. 2020
methanol and hexane extracts	CUPRAC (EC ₅₀ = 20.29 µg/mL), FRAP (EC ₅₀ = 43.38 µg/mL); amylase (0.79 mmol ACAE/g), glucosidase (3.75 mmol ACAE/g) inhibition; and tyrosinase inhibition with lowest IC ₅₀ value (21.11 µg/mL)	El Aanachi et al. 2020
essential oil	DPPH IC ₅₀ = 83.26 µg/mL; FRAP IC ₅₀ = 116.42 µg/mL; ABTS IC ₅₀ = 132.25 µg/mL; H ₂ O ₂ IC ₅₀ = 48.67 µg/mL; 5-lipoxygenase inhibition (IC ₅₀ = 39.31 µg/mL)	Al-Mijalli et al. 2022
essential oil	AChE IC ₅₀ = 10.5 mg/mL	Fayoumi et al. 2022
essential oil	AChE IC ₅₀ = 47.70 µg/mL, BuChE IC ₅₀ = 50.03 µg/mL; COX-1 IC ₅₀ = 11 µg/mL; COX-2 IC ₅₀ = 50 µg/mL	Karadağ et al. 2023
Methanol-aqueous extract	DPPH (273.45 mg TE/g), ABTS ⁺ (531.97 mg TE/g), CUPRAC (431.32 mg TE/g), FRAP (292.21 mg TE/g), metal chelating capacity (13.44 EDTAE/g), phosphomolybdenum assay (2.71 mmol TE/g), AChE (2.80 mg GALAE/g), BuChE (2.20 mg GALAE/g), tyrosinase (75.49 mg KAE/g), α-glucosidase (3.75 mmol ACAE/g), α-amylase (0.79 mmol ACAE/g), lipase inhibition (28.91 mg OE/g); AChE (2.80 mg GALAE/g) and BChE inhibition (2.20 mg GALAE/g)	Gevenrova et al. 2024
essential oil/aqueous and ethanol extracts	DPPH IC ₅₀ > 2/0.13/0.05 mg/mL; reducing power 21.77/3.01/1.92 ASE/mL; Fe ²⁺ chelating activity IC ₅₀ > 2/NA/> 2 mg/mL	M'hamdi et al. 2024
essential oil	DPPH IC ₅₀ = 22.93 µg/mL; FRAP IC ₅₀ = 18.79 µg/mL	Draiaia et al. 2025
Antibacterial and antiviral activity		
essential oil/extract	Inhibition against <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> ,	Androutsopoulou et al. 2021
essential oil	Inhibition against <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	Jaradat et al. 2022
essential oil	Inhibition against <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> and <i>E. coli</i>	Fayoumi et al. 2022
essential oil	inhibition against Gram ⁺ and Gram ⁻ strains (<i>E. coli</i> , <i>Proteus mirabilis</i> , <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> , <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>)	Al-Mijalli et al. 2022
essential oil/different extracts	Inhibition against Gram ⁺ and Gram ⁻ strains (<i>Streptococcus</i> spp., <i>Staphylococcus</i> spp., <i>Bacillus</i> spp., <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> , <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> , <i>Mariniluteicoccus flavus</i>)	Amel et al. 2022
Antifungal activity		
essential oil/extract	Inhibition against <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Androutsopoulou et al. 2021
Pure/essential oil	Inhibition against <i>Candida</i> sp.	Ferreira et al. 2021; Rosato et al. 2021
Antiviral activity		
essential oil/extract	Suppression of Adenovirus 35	Androutsopoulou et al. 2021
essential oil	Antiviral activity against Ross River virus (RRV)	Sandasi et al. 2023
Anticancer activity		
essential oil	Breast cancer - MCF-7 cells: induction of cell cycle arrest and apoptosis (dose 60 µg/ml), regulation of AMPK/mTOR pathway (dose 42.8, 90.2, and 73.9 µg/ml); MDA-MB-231 cells: anti-metastatic function, anti-angiogenesis, and cytotoxic potentials (dose 4 µL/mL)	Amel et al. 2022
ethanol extract/essential oil	Lung cancer – A549 cells: growth inhibition and larvicidal activities (46.72 µg/mL); NCI-H460 cells: cytotoxicity and DNA damage (GI ₅₀ = 81.4 µg/mL)	Amel et al. 2022
essential oil	Colon cancer - HCT-15 cells: inducing cytotoxicity and DNA damage (GI ₅₀ = 63.7 ± 1.39 µg/mL); HCT 116 cells: IC ₅₀ = 74 mg/mL, determined by MTT cell viability assay Colon adenocarcinoma - HT-29 cells: suppress the proliferation by inducing apoptosis (IC ₅₀ = 195.33 ± 5.4 µg/ml)	Amel et al. 2022; Fayoumi et al. 2022
essential oil	Gastric cancer - AGS cells: anti-metastatic function, anti-angiogenesis, and cytotoxic potentials (dose 4 µL/mL);	
essential oil	cervical carcinoma - HeLa cells: inducing cytotoxicity and DNA damage (GI ₅₀ = 70.9 ± 0.04 µg/mL)	
essential oil	Melanoma - B16F10 cells: Inhibition of L-tyrosine hydroxylation and L-DOPA oxidation enzyme activity (dose-dependent manner); MV3 cells: anti-metastatic function, anti-angiogenesis, and cytotoxic potentials (dose 4 µL/mL); SK-MEL-3: antioxidative activity and decreasing the tyrosinase activity (dose XTT50 = 45 µU/mL);	Amel et al. 2022
Reproductive activity		
essential oil/ethanol-aqueous extract	suppressed the oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation, promoting sperm quality, motility, viability and morphology, and preventing testicular oxidative damage (compared to vit. E) Reduced the testicular damage induced by lead acetate, resulting in a significant increase in sperm amount	Sandasi et al. 2023
Antidiabetic activity		
essential oil	α-glucosidase inhibition: IC ₅₀ = 93.72 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 80.4 µg/mL (acarbose)	Ahamad and Uthirapathy 2021
ethanol extract	Improvement of glucose tolerance of alloxan-treated diabetic rats	Al-Hamdani and Ali 2022
essential oil	α-glucosidase inhibition: IC ₅₀ = 19.04 µg/mL; α-amylase IC ₅₀ = 43.33 µg/mL	Al-Mijalli et al. 2022
essential oil	150 mg/kg bw dose reduced catalase, superoxide dismutase, and glutathione peroxidase in the liver and kidneys, and lipid peroxidation	Sandasi et al. 2023
essential oil	42.5 mg/kg bw dose for 3 weeks decreased blood glucose level, and lipid peroxi and restored antioxidant enzyme activities	Sandasi et al. 2023
Neuroprotective activity		
essential oil	Protection from methomyl-induced memory impairment in rats	M'hammed Amine et al. 2020
Insecticidal/repellent activity		
essential oil	Oviposition deterrent effect against <i>Drosophila suzukii</i>	Bošković et al. 2023
essential oil	insecticidal activity against the house fly (<i>Musca domestica</i>) - lethal dose of 19 µg/fly and against food mite (<i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i>) - LD ₅₀ = 4.17 µg/cm ²	Sandasi et al. 2023
	repellent effect of more than 90% of the ticks at 0.103 mg/cm ² against the lone star tick (<i>Amblyomma americanum</i>)	Sandasi et al. 2023

Compound/Extract	Results	Reference
essential oil	inhibition and the oviposition of the silverleaf whitefly (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>) on tomato leaflets at 0.5% concentration	Sandasi et al. 2023
essential oil	acaricidal activity towards the cattle tick (<i>Rhipicephalus microplus</i>) with 73% to 95% concentration-dependent efficacy	Sandasi et al. 2023
essential oil	acute toxicity towards <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> larvae in a topical-application assay with LD ₅₀ = 1.13 µg/mg per insect and LD ₉₀ = 2.56 µg/mg per insect	Sandasi et al. 2023
essential oil/aqueous and ethanol extracts	insecticidal activity against rice weevils (<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>); essential oil had the highest activity: 100% mortality of rice weevils	M'hamdi et al. 2024
Cosmetic properties		
essential oil	sebum-reducing potential	Sandasi et al. 2023

Stage-specific variation in antioxidant activity has also been described (Al-Mijalli et al. 2022). As a result, the essential oil at the full flowering stage showed the best antioxidant activity, with IC₅₀ values of 83.26, 116.42, 132.25, and 48.67 µg/mL in DPPH, FRAP, ABTS, and H₂O₂ assays, respectively (Table 2).

The literature provides both traditional and experimental evidence of anti-inflammatory properties (Amel et al. 2022). In vitro enzyme-inhibitory tests also support anti-inflammatory potential and cholinesterase inhibition, attributed to terpenes including geraniol (Karadağ et al. 2023) (Table 2). The IC₅₀ values of geraniol for COX-1, COX-2, and 5-LOX were 11.17, 8.1, and 7 µg/mL, respectively, while for the extract the corresponding values were 11.13, > 50, and 23.1 µg/mL. Additionally, the same study revealed cholinesterase inhibition with IC₅₀ values of 47.70 µg/mL (AChE) and 50.03 µg/mL (BuChE), while geraniol showed IC₅₀ values of 16.78 µg/mL (AChE) and 9.11 µg/mL (BuChE) (Karadağ et al. 2023). Another study on the methanol-aqueous leaf extract reported anti-AChE (2.80 mg GALAE/g) and anti-BChE (2.20 mg GALAE/g) activity (Gevrenova et al. 2024) (Table 2).

Furthermore, the oil exhibited significant inhibitory effects against α-amylase (IC₅₀ = 43.33 µg/mL), α-glucosidase (IC₅₀ = 19.04 µg/mL), lipase (IC₅₀ = 24.33 µg/mL), 5-lipoxygenase (IC₅₀ = 39.31 µg/mL), and tyrosinase (IC₅₀ = 124.49 µg/mL) (Al-Mijalli et al. 2022).

Previously, El Aanachi et al. (2020) reported that *P. graveolens* methanol extract showed the strongest anti-tyrosinase effect (IC₅₀ = 21.11 µg/mL), as well as α-amylase (0.79 mmol ACAE/g) and α-glucosidase (3.75 mmol ACAE/g) inhibitory activity (Table 2).

For the methanol-aqueous extract, tyrosinase (75.49 mg KAE/g), amylase (0.79 mmol ACAE/g), glucosidase (3.75 mmol ACAE/g), and lipase (28.91 mg OE/g) inhibitory activities were also reported (Gevrenova et al. 2024) (Table 2). Methoxylated flavanols and related derivatives may be associated with anti-BChE, anti-AChE, and anti-tyrosinase activity, while caftaric acid along with hydroxycinnamic acid conjugates and phenolic acid-hexosides accounted for the α-glucosidase inhibitory activity.

The anti-inflammatory activity of the essential oil was further evaluated in three different setups, including albumin denaturation, heat-induced hemolysis, and nitric oxide scavenging activity, where a dose-dependent response was observed in all assays. Dose-dependent AChE inhibition with an IC₅₀ value of 10.5 mg/mL was also confirmed, emphasizing the anti-Alzheimer's potential (Fayoumi et al. 2022) (Table 2).

Antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral activity

Numerous studies have reported strong antibacterial and antifungal effects, attributed mainly to essential oil components such as citronellol and geraniol, together with phenolic compounds (Sandasi et al. 2023). A comprehensive review confirmed the traditional antimicrobial uses (Amel et al. 2022) (Table 2).

A study of rose geranium oil of Palestinian origin highlighted antimicrobial activity against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* (Jaradat et al. 2022), while another work emphasized antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* (Androustoupoulou et al. 2021) (Table 2).

Extracts of *P. graveolens* also showed activity against *Escherichia coli*, *S. aureus*, and *C. albicans* (Androustoupoulou et al. 2021; Pedraza et al. 2023). Likewise, the essential oil and various extracts were screened against numerous microorganisms, including *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, and *Bacillus* species, as well as *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Mariniluteicoccus flavus* (Al-Mijalli et al. 2022; Amel et al. 2022; Fayoumi et al. 2022) (Table 2).

Rosato et al. (2021) reported the synergistic effect of rose geranium essential oil with diclofenac sodium salt on the growth of *Candida* spp., with high sensitivity detected to the compounds tested, both individually and in combination. Another study described the clinical efficacy of an essential oil mouth rinse in treating oral candidiasis (Ferreira et al. 2021) (Table 2).

Moreover, *P. graveolens* essential oil and extract were tested against Adenovirus 35 (Androustoupoulou et al. 2021). Both demonstrated strong antiviral activity. Rose geranium oil also showed significant potential against Ross River virus (RRV), with antiviral activity observed when applied prior to, during, or after infection (Sandasi et al. 2023) (Table 2).

Anticancer activity

Rose geranium essential oil exhibited prominent cytotoxicity against HCT 116 human colon cancer cells, with an IC₅₀ value of 74 µg/mL determined by the MTT assay (Fayoumi et al. 2022). A wide range of cancer cell lines, including breast, lung, gastric, colon, and cervical cancers, as well as melanoma, have also been treated with the oil (Amel et al. 2022) (Table 2).

Neuroprotective effect

M'hammed Amine et al. (2020) evaluated the protective role of *P. graveolens* essential oil in a methomyl-induced model, examining spatial working memory (SWM), oxidative stress parameters, and histopathological changes in the hippocampus. The data revealed that supplementation with the essential oil improved SWM, partially restored antioxidant system activities, and prevented neuronal cell damage (Table 2).

Reproductive activity

Rose geranium oil and ethanol-aqueous extract have been tested for reproductive and spermatogenesis properties (Sandasi et al. 2023). The oil suppressed oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation, thereby improving sperm quality, motility, viability, and morphology while preventing testicular oxidative damage. In addition, the alcoholic extract reduced testicular damage induced by lead acetate and resulted in a marked increase in sperm count compared to the control (Table 2).

Antidiabetic activity

P. graveolens leaves essential oil at concentrations from 31.25 to 1000 µg/mL inhibited α -glucosidase from 28.13 to 74.24%, respectively (Ahamad and Uthirapathy 2021). The IC_{50} values for *P. graveolens* and acarbose were 93.72 ± 4.76 µg/mL and 80.4 ± 2.17 µg/mL, respectively. Rose geranium ethanolic extract also improved glucose tolerance and hepatic glycogen content in diabetic rats without affecting insulin concentration (Al-Hamdani and Ali 2022) (Table 2).

A monograph by Sandasi et al. (2023) reviewed antidiabetic studies on the species. In one study, rose geranium oil was orally administered to alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The higher dose of 150 mg/kg bw produced a significant antidiabetic effect compared to the lower dose (75 mg/kg bw), decreasing antioxidant enzyme activities for catalase, superoxide dismutase, and glutathione peroxidase in the liver and kidneys, and reducing lipid peroxidation. Likewise, another study showed that 42.5 mg/kg bw essential oil administered for 3 weeks significantly decreased blood glucose and lipid peroxidation while restoring antioxidant enzyme activities in alloxan-induced diabetic rats (Sandasi et al. 2023) (Table 2).

Insecticidal/repellent activity

The insecticidal activity of *P. graveolens* essential oil has been associated with its monoterpene content (Bošković et al. 2023). A monograph on the species by Sandasi et al. (2023) highlighted that rose geranium oil demonstrates a strong repelling effect. The acaricidal activity of geranium oil has been investigated against the housefly (*Musca domestica*), with a lethal dose of 19 µg/fly, and against the food mite (*Tyrophagus putrescentiae*), with high toxicity of $LD_{50} = 4.17$ µg/cm³ (Sandasi et al. 2023) (Table 2).

Another study evaluated the insecticidal effect against the lone star tick (*Amblyomma americanum*) and found that 10-*epi*- γ -eudesmol had the highest activity, with more than 90% of ticks repelled at 0.103 mg/cm² (Sandasi et al. 2023). Moreover, Sandasi et al. (2023) reported inhibition of oviposition of the silverleaf whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*) on tomato leaflets by *P. graveolens* essential oil at 0.5% concentration, as well as acaricidal activity against the cattle tick (*Rhipicephalus microplus*) with 73%–95% concentration-dependent efficacy. Acute toxicity was also observed against *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae in a topical-application assay, with $LD_{50} = 1.13$ µg/mg per insect and $LD_{90} = 2.56$ µg/mg per insect (Sandasi et al. 2023) (Table 2).

Another study confirmed the insecticidal effect by testing the toxicity of rose geranium essential oil and extracts against rice weevils (*Sitophilus oryzae*). The essential oil showed the highest activity compared to aqueous and ethanolic extracts (M'hamdi et al. 2024).

Cosmetic properties

Rose geranium oil has been applied for cosmetic purposes, showing good sebum-reducing potential comparable to that of a known sebostatic, 3% niacinamide (Sandasi et al. 2023). Due to its pleasant aroma, the oil is also used as an ingredient in massage oils, skin care creams, soaps, deodorants, toothpaste, and other cosmetic products (Brenes et al. 2024) (Table 2).

Conclusion

Pelargonium graveolens is a rich source of bioactive compounds, particularly monoterpene alcohols such as citronellol and geraniol, as well as a diverse array of flavonoids and phenolic acids, including acyltartaric and acylcitric acids. Rose geranium extracts and oils, characterized by the described phytochemical composition, exhibit a broad spectrum of pharmacological activities, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory, anticancer and neuroprotective activity, as well as antidiabetic, antimicrobial, and insecticidal effects. A significant inhibitory capacity towards α -glucosidase has been revealed, which evokes further interest in its use as a promising natural source for managing hyperglycemia. These findings support the traditional use of *P. graveolens* in herbal medicine and highlight its potential for the development of natural therapeutic agents in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Vessela Balabanova: Conceptualization; Methodology; Investigation; Resources; Data curation; Writing - Original draft preparation; Project administration; Funding acquisition; Dimitrina Zheleva-Dimitrova: Visualization; Writing - Review & Editing; Reneta Gevrenova: Investigation; Data curation; Writing - Original draft, Review & Editing; Supervision.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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